

Haptic feedback and assistance for off-highway machinery

Challenges & solutions:

Haption devised several devices and feedback schemes suited for off-highway machinery human-machine interfaces.

First, to provide haptic assistance to driving tracked vehicles, we designed haptic-enabled track control levers featuring force and tactile feedback in the lever handles. This enables co-location of haptic feedback related to driving tasks with the controls used for driving. They provide assisted braking, steering and cruise-control through force-feedback, and information on obstacle avoidance and path following through tactile cues.

Second, we designed a fully configurable 6 degree-of-freedom (DoF) force-feedback joystick to provide haptic assistance for tool manipulation. With DoF independently lockable in software, the joystick enables the implementation of control kinematics for a diverse set of tools. Interchangeable handles provide a perfect fit to control each type of vehicle control constraints. Vibrotactile feedback in the handle provide tactile notifications in addition to force feedback. The joystick enables co-location of haptic feedback related to tool manipulation tasks with the controls used for handling the tool. Force-feedback enables collision avoidance, keeps tools within a safe manipulation area, and provides clear perception of tool axis limits and applied loads.

Tactile feedback in the handle notifies operators of tool axis limits, provides task-relevant event notifications and proximity warnings for guidance.

Impact:

Our results have the potential to significantly assist off-highway vehicle operators both in driving and tool manipulation tasks, in a wide variety of settings. Next steps will include validating and refining haptic feedback schemes, and deploying the technical solutions to a wider range of application domains.

Figure 1: Devices from Haption

KEY BENEFITS

Intuitive torque and tactile feedback for guidance during driving

Intuitive handling of tools through customizable control kinematics

Clearer perception of machine limits and loads

